

RHEOCHOR OF BINARY MIXTURES

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It has been observed that the mixture law is applicable to rheochor in case of non-associated binary mixtures.

In several papers from this laboratory (this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 29; 1948, 25, 163, 575, 691; 1949, 26, 533; 1950, 27, 283, 345; 1951, 28, 275; 1952, 29, 303, 691, 706), we have tried to apply the mixture law in case of rheochor. The work has been extended in this paper. The expression employed is

$$R_m = \frac{M_m \gamma^k}{D}$$

where $R_m = (1-x)R + xR_x$ and $M_m = (1-x)M + xM_x$; R_m , M_m , R_x , γ , and D are the rheochor of the solution, mean M.W of the solution, rheochor of the solute, viscosity of the solution, and density of the solution respectively. Our results are summarised in Tables I—IV.

TABLE I
Rheochor of benzene in toluene.

x	Temp. = 30°.			Temp. = 40°.			Temp. = 50°.		
	D	$\gamma \times 10^3$	R_x	D	$\gamma \times 10^3$	R_x	D	$\gamma \times 10^3$	R_x
0.0000	0.8467	5.238	..	0.8353	4.700	..	0.8239	4.213	..
0.1316	0.8473	5.318	112.7	0.8399	4.740	110.2	0.8292	4.241	110.2
0.2504	0.8507	5.326	110.4	0.8443	4.775	108.1	0.8334	4.187	111.0
0.3857	0.8541	5.353	110.6	0.8493	4.795	110.6	0.8374	4.292	110.1
0.5971	0.8583	5.426	110.2	0.8516	4.823	111.2	0.8399	4.315	109.8
0.8778	0.8610	5.537	109.9	0.8528	4.857	110.3	0.8429	4.330	111.1
1.0000	0.8640	5.638	..	0.8551	4.892	..	0.8450	4.341	..

$R_{obs} = 110.0$. $R_{calc} = 109.8$.

TABLE II
Rheochor of methylethyl ketone in toluene.

x	Temp. = 30°.			Temp. = 40°.			Temp. = 50°.		
	D	$\gamma \times 10^3$	R_x	D	$\gamma \times 10^3$	R_x	D	$\gamma \times 10^3$	R_x
0.0000	0.8467	5.238	..	0.8352	4.700	..	0.8239	4.213	..
0.1636	0.8427	5.173	108.2	0.8318	4.673	107.9	0.8192	4.160	108.0
0.2714	0.8350	5.028	108.4	0.8246	4.536	108.4	0.8136	4.020	108.2
0.4439	0.8295	4.888	108.0	0.8185	4.436	108.2	0.8086	3.895	108.0
0.5380	0.8230	4.738	108.4	0.8123	4.326	108.6	0.8015	3.865	108.3
0.7025	0.8150	4.608	108.5	0.8104	4.310	108.4	0.7826	3.605	108.4
0.8145	0.8122	4.463	108.0	0.8093	4.298	108.9	0.7800	3.465	109.0
1.0000	0.7980	4.365	..	0.7842	4.050	..	0.7706	3.273	..

$R_{obs} = 108.4$. $R_{calc} = 108.4$.

TABLE III
Rheochor of benzene in CCl₄.

<i>x.</i>	Temp. = 30°.			Temp. = 40°.			Temp. = 50°.		
	<i>D.</i>	$\gamma \times 10^3$.	<i>R_x</i> .	<i>D.</i>	$\gamma \times 10^3$.	<i>R_x</i> .	<i>D.</i>	$\gamma \times 10^3$.	<i>R_x</i> .
0.0000	1.6300	8.390	..	1.6160	7.400	..	1.5860	6.580	..
0.1523	1.5200	7.586	109.8	1.4920	6.546	109.8	1.4630	5.598	109.7
0.2945	1.3930	6.252	109.6	1.3650	5.200	109.4	1.3400	4.750	109.6
0.4114	1.2950	5.571	109.6	1.2850	5.115	109.6	1.2560	4.414	109.6
0.5824	1.1800	5.373	109.2	1.1600	4.708	109.4	1.1450	3.988	109.6
0.7230	1.0780	5.208	109.2	1.0600	4.536	109.5	1.0580	3.810	109.5
0.8608	0.9557	5.000	109.3	0.9572	4.312	109.3	0.9408	3.750	109.2
1.0000	0.8638	4.804	..	0.8541	4.244	..	0.8448	3.662	..

$$R_{\text{obs}}=109.4 \quad R_{\text{calc}}=109.8.$$

TABLE IV
Rheochor of methylethyl ketone in CCl₄.

<i>x.</i>	Temp. = 30°.			Temp. = 40°.			Temp. = 50°.		
	<i>D.</i>	$\gamma \times 10^3$.	<i>R_x</i> .	<i>D.</i>	$\gamma \times 10^3$.	<i>R_x</i> .	<i>D.</i>	$\gamma \times 10^3$.	<i>R_x</i> .
0.0000	1.6300	8.390	..	1.6160	7.400	..	1.5860	6.580	..
0.1725	1.4980	7.563	108.2	1.4720	6.502	108.2	1.4400	5.582	108.3
0.3108	1.3670	6.232	108.4	1.3370	5.187	108.2	1.3240	4.625	108.2
0.4393	1.2510	5.460	108.6	1.2410	5.000	108.2	1.2160	4.375	108.4
0.5820	1.1370	5.000	108.0	1.1340	4.896	108.4	1.1320	4.175	108.6
0.7219	1.0290	4.826	108.0	1.0240	4.658	108.2	1.0002	3.892	108.0
0.8642	0.9237	4.578	108.2	0.9065	4.316	108.2	0.8853	3.596	108.2
1.0000	0.7980	4.365	..	0.7842	4.050	..	0.7706	3.273	..

$$R_{\text{obs}}=108.2 \quad R_{\text{calc}}=108.4$$

It will be seen therefore that the mixture law is applicable in case of non-associated liquids studied in this paper.